
The Law and the Philosopher. On Leo Strauss' "The Law of Reason in the *Kuzari*"

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Abstract: This paper presents an interpretation of Leo Strauss' essay on Yehuda Halevi's *Kuzari* that focuses on reading it as a philosophic text in its own right. It argues that Leo Strauss uses the *Kuzari* to show the central importance the question of a fully rational law has for an adequate understanding of the relationship between philosophy and society. Strauss presents the philosophic view as ultimately denying any absolute obligations based on moral laws and puts it in opposition to a position that claims the law to be obligatory not as rational, but as divinely revealed.

Keywords: Leo Strauss, Yehuda Halevi, Kuzari, Philosophic Life, Political Philosophy.

1. Introduction

Leo Strauss' Essay "The Law of Reason in the *Kuzari*" is without doubt one of his less known works*. This is hardly surprising, as it appears – at least at first glance – to be a merely scholarly discussion of Yehuda Halevi's *Kuzari*, a somewhat obscure work of medieval Jewish literature. But already at the beginning of his essay, Strauss indicates that he has more in mind than a work of scholarship when he poses the question of "what philosophy is or what a philosopher is" (LRK §1, p. 95).¹ This question, Strauss continues, can only be resolved through a discussion of the Natural Law or, more specifically, of the possibility of a rational law, a Law of Reason.

This paper focuses on Strauss' understanding of this "Law of Reason" and its relationship to philosophy and the philosopher. In the first part, I will discuss the term "Law of Reason" in comparison to other terms employed by Strauss in his essay, namely "Natural Law" and the "rational *nomoi*." Then I will turn to the Law of Reason both as the philosophic law and as the basis for every law. Afterwards, Strauss' hypothetical interpretation of Halevi as what one may call a "lapsed" philosopher will be discussed. I will conclude with the question of Strauss' intention in posing the question of "what a philosopher is" specifically in the context of his essay on the *Kuzari*.

Yehuda Halevi, the author of the *Kuzari*, was an important Jewish poet who lived in the Islamic part of Spain during the late 11th and early 12th century CE.² The *Kuzari* is his most famous work and has to this day remained an important part of the Jewish literal tradition.³ It presents

mainly a dialogue between a Jewish Scholar and the king of the Khazars, the eponymous "Kuzari," which results in the latter's conversion to Judaism. As such the book can be called an example of Jewish apologetics because Halevi presents various other religious positions that are then refuted by the Jewish scholar. The setting of the dialogue itself is based on the historical conversion of the Khazars, a nomadic people that ruled a kingdom in the Caucasus region between the 7th and 10th century CE.⁴ Halevi possibly drew on older accounts of this event, but the dialogue itself is entirely fictional.⁵ The main interlocutors relevant for the discussion in this paper will be the philosopher, the Jewish scholar, and the king of the Khazars.

Strauss published his essay on the *Kuzari* first in 1943 and later included it in the collection *Persecution and the Art of Writing*, where it is situated between the essays on Maimonides' *Guide for the Perplexed* and Spinoza's *Theologico-Political Treatise*, respectively.⁶ As such, it forms the central part of a triad of essays that all discuss works of Jewish authors on law. But while the other two parts are mainly concerned with divinely revealed law and specifically the Bible, the essay on the *Kuzari* discusses the Law of Reason, i.e. the law of the philosophers.

Despite this prominent place in Strauss' oeuvre, the essay on the *Kuzari* has generally found only moderate scholarly interest compared to books like *Natural Right and History*.⁷ Recently, Laurence Lampert published a substantial interpretation of the "The Law of Reason in the *Kuzari*" that assigns the essay a central role in Strauss' "embrace [of] exotericism".⁸ Lampert's reading would warrant a detailed discussion that goes beyond what this paper is trying to accomplish. I will thus refer to it only when it immediately applies to the argument presented here.

2. The Law of Reason

Strauss begins his essay by contrasting two opposing understandings of the "Natural Law," a term that, as he adds, "is as indispensable as it is open to grave objections" (LRK §1, 95). Citing the medieval author Marsilius of Padua, Strauss presents what he calls "the philosophic view" of the *ius naturale* (LRK §3, p. 97), which identifies the Natural Law with those moral rules that are accepted by many different political communities (LRK §2-4, pp. 95-98). As such these rules can, however, only me-

taphorically be called natural, because they are based on mere convention that may or may not have a rational, i.e. natural, foundation. They are only, as Marsilius puts it, “quasi-natural”.⁹ The other view, which Strauss calls “perhaps (...) the theological view” (LRK §3, p. 98), is represented by Thomas Aquinas. It amounts to the supposition that natural laws are inherent in human rationality (*rationi inditum*) and, as such, non-conventional and universally binding. It is noteworthy that from the beginning of the essay, Strauss frames the question of the Natural Law as a dichotomy between a theological view, on the one hand and a philosophic or, as one might add, anti-theological view, on the other. Against the authority of Marsilius of Padua and Thomas Aquinas, Strauss calls upon Yehuda Halevi, who seems to contradict the “impression that the philosophers (...) denied the rational character of the Natural Law” (LKR §4, p. 98). Halevi, in other words, appears to present in his dialogue a philosopher who asserts the existence of a rational law, a Law of Reason.

Strauss’ term “Law of Reason” is a peculiar terminological choice. It is deliberately meant to confuse the reader, since Strauss uses “Law of Reason,” “rational laws,” or “rational *nomoi*,” among others, which sound similar at first, with various meanings. Therefore, the reader of the essay is always required to consider the context in which Strauss uses these different terms, as their meaning shifts while the argument progresses. In addition, while one might expect the title-giving “Law of Reason” to be a term taken from the *Kuzari*, Halevi never actually uses it. Strauss indicates this by only referring to “rational laws” or, most prominently, “rational *nomoi*” when he directly cites the *Kuzari*.¹⁰ By using a general philosophic term not directly employed by Halevi, Strauss shows that his interpretation of Halevi’s teaching serves to illuminate the general philosophic question of the relationship between reason and law and has to be understood as doing so.

But even the seemingly more “historical” term “rational *nomoi*” serves a rhetorical purpose and is not merely a direct translation from the *Kuzari*. As Strauss points out in a footnote: “The term employed by Halevi (...) means literally ‘the intellectual *nomoi*.’ I am not at all certain whether this literal translation is not the more adequate one.” (LRK §4, p. 98 n. 8). The reason for Strauss’ decision in favor of the less literal translation becomes clear, when he later points out that “Plato’s *Laws* were known in Halevi’s period as Plato’s rational *nomoi*” (LRK §20, p. 116). When speaking of the “rational *nomoi*” as *the* philosophic position, Strauss has a specific philosophic position in mind, namely the one taken by ancient philosophy and especially Platonic philosophy.

3. The rational *nomoi* of the philosophers

What do we have to understand by these “rational *nomoi*”? To answer this question, Strauss begins with the explanation the philosopher gives to the king of the Khazars in the first part of the *Kuzari* (LRK §16-21, pp. 112-118). According to this account, the rational *nomoi* seem primarily intended to regulate the life of philosophers. This regulation is based on an understanding of human

nature that sees philosophy as the highest perfection of man. The rational *nomoi* “have been set up by the philosophers with a view to the unchanging needs of man as man” (LRK §20, p. 116). The life of the philosopher consists essentially in theoretical contemplation and seems as such completely disinterested in any social interaction beyond the barest minimum. “The philosopher denies the relevance (...) of all actions; more precisely, he asserts the superiority of contemplation as such to action as such” (LRK §18, p. 114). Strauss can thus call the rational *nomoi* with some justification a “*regimen solitarii*” (LRK §20, p. 116), a regulation for the life of a hermit.

But in his dialogue with the king, the philosopher cannot completely deny the relevance of social interactions, especially as the king is deeply concerned with social, or, more precisely, political and religious matters. The king, prompted by a prophetic dream, wants to know which religion he should adopt for himself and his country. To this question the philosopher answers in a manner that seems to reveal a complete agnosticism: He advises the king to decide this question based purely on practical expediency. The king might simply remain in his ancestral religion, he might choose one of the existing religions for himself, or he might even invent an entirely new religion. As Strauss points out: “The religious indifference of the philosopher knows no limits” (LRK §19, p. 115).

Strangely enough, the philosopher also presents a fourth option to the king: to adopt the rational *nomoi* of the philosophers as his own religion. We learn that the rational *nomoi* are “identical with ‘the religion of the philosophers’” (LRK §20, p. 116). How can this statement be understood in light of the philosopher’s supposed complete religious indifference? It soon becomes clear that this indifference only concerns outward actions, the adherence to this or that religious ceremony and creed. Regarding divine revelation, the philosopher is far from indifferent. Rather, he completely denies divine revelation, or, as Strauss defines it, “information given by God immediately to human beings concerning the kind of action which is pleasing to him” (LRK §9, p. 103). The philosopher primarily denies God as a lawgiver. According to his theology, “God has no likes or dislikes, no wish or will of any kind” (LRK §18, p. 113). The philosopher thus interprets God in accordance with his general understanding of the highest excellence consisting not in action, but in contemplation.

The rational *nomoi* of the philosophers can accordingly be called a religion because they have a certain set of theological implications. But there is another aspect that ties them to religion. As Strauss later points out, “philosophy presupposes social life” in the sense that a contemplative way of life is only possible in a society that provides enough leisure for it (LRK §44, p. 139). Because the philosopher cannot ignore his social environment, his rational *nomoi* have to include a “governmental part” (LRK §43, p. 138), a political component that regulates his relations with others. The full meaning of this governmental part is, as Strauss shows, spelled out only by the Jewish scholar, and not by the philosopher himself (LRK §24, pp. 120-121). As an enemy of philosophy, the scholar can state clearly what the philosopher is reluctant to reveal in public. The rational *nomoi* of the philosophers turn out to have both an “exoteric” (LRK §24, p. 121),

that is, political teaching directed at non-philosophers and an “esoteric” meaning intended for potential philosophers who are capable of disentangling it from the teaching as a whole. But, as Strauss makes clear, not every philosopher weighs these elements in the same manner. While some may limit their rational *nomoi* to “an essentially apolitical rule of conduct,” others may present an “essentially political code” (LRK §20, p. 116). This code is intended not only for the guidance of potential philosophers, but also encompasses legislation for a particular political community. As such, though, the exoteric teaching has to convince the citizens of a specific community.

The rational *nomoi* can then be understood both as a set of laws for a particular political community and as a personal code of conduct for the life of the philosopher (LRK §20, pp. 115-117). As a set of political laws, the rational *nomoi* have to demand obedience from the citizens of the political community, which they are supposed to regulate. For this purpose, they require a different basis than pure rationality, as not all – or even most – citizens will be able to understand the view of the philosophers rationally. The philosophers are forced to invent religious myths to support their rational *nomoi*, giving them the form of a religion. As an “essentially political code,” the rational *nomoi* therefore contain “a political theology” (LRK §20, p. 116).¹¹ This religion, despite being invented by philosophers, can never be called fully rational, as it will by necessity include elements that are politically useful, but not theoretically sound (LRK §23-24, pp. 119-121). Strauss makes this very clear by singling out “that God is a lawgiver” as a theological teaching the philosopher “must consider untrue” (LRK §24, p. 121), a position that is obviously incompatible with the alleged divine origin of the civil laws proclaimed by the philosophers. Their religion “is, at best, a likely tale” (LRK §24, p. 121).

The philosophers do not consider the rational *nomoi* obligatory, either as a political legislation or as a personal code of conduct. Both aspects stand in the service of the philosophic way of life. They “have been set up by the philosophers with a view to the unchanging needs of man as man; they are codes fixing the political or other conditions most favorable to the highest perfection of man” (LRK §20, p. 116). And the legislative aspect of the rational *nomoi* is ultimately not a necessary element for them: “The philosopher’s law is not necessarily a political law” (LRK §20, pp. 116-117). Their concern is the “philosophic life” (LRK §20, p. 117), which is distinguished from – if not contrary to – the political life.¹²

4. The Law of Reason and the Natural Law

The Jewish scholar – of course – rejects the rational *nomoi* of the philosophers, as he believes in the truth of the divinely revealed Jewish Law. But surprisingly enough, his rejection is only a partial rejection. By comparing the different statements of the scholar, Strauss shows that the scholar uses the term “rational *nomoi*” in an ambiguous way (LRK §29-41, pp. 118-135). On the one hand, there are the rational *nomoi* meant as a “complete code,” which the scholar rejects, but on the other hand,

there are the rational *nomoi* understood as a “framework of every code,” which he accepts as true (LRK §42, p. 136). This distinction is possible because the scholar tacitly separates the *regimen solitarii* of the philosophers from its “governmental part” (LRK §43, p. 138), the part of the rational *nomoi* that is concerned with regulating the social relations of the philosopher (LRK §42-44, pp. 135-139). While being a necessary element of the “Law of Reason,” i.e. the complete code taught by the philosophers, this “governmental part” is separable because it is based on the necessities underlying all social relationships.

These necessities form the “framework of every code” of law and are what Strauss now calls the “Natural Law” in contradistinction to the “Law of Reason” (LRK §42, p. 136). This Natural Law cannot be called fully rational, “if universal validity is taken as an unambiguous sign of rationality” (LRK §37, p. 133). When we consider the opposition between the “quasi-natural,” i.e. commonly accepted laws, and the Natural Law as a rational and obligatory law, as Strauss had presented it at the beginning of his essay (LRK §2, pp. 95-96), it becomes evident that what Strauss now calls the Natural Law is largely in accordance with the position of the quasi-natural laws. The commonly accepted laws are not rational because they have no fixed, universally obligatory content. But what can come to be accepted in a society is limited by the aspirations and needs of its members, i.e. by human nature. This is the point in which this second statement on the quasi-natural laws differs from the first statement. While formerly these laws had appeared as only an agglomeration of commonly held, but ultimately arbitrary laws, the Natural Law now becomes clear as a set of “elementary rules of social conduct which have to be observed equally by all communities, by the most noble community as well as by a gang of robbers” (LRK §20, p. 116).

The concept of the Natural Law as a “framework of every code” can then be summed up in the following manner: Reason is able to supply standards for the distinction of good and bad laws insofar as the maintenance of a specific social community is concerned. But these laws cannot be judged outside of their concrete context and therefore cannot be universalized. They cannot even be understood as strictly obligatory, as Strauss demonstrates through the case of the prohibition of lying. Every society has to proscribe lying to some extent, but at the same time the philosophers as inventors of political religions are shown to be lying about the very foundation of political society.

Furthermore, the Natural Law as a mere sum of rules necessary for any kind of association is by itself insufficient to support a political community. This becomes clear when we consider the opposition between a “gang of robbers” and the “most noble community” cited before. A gang of robbers, or any association purely directed towards promoting the individual interests of its members, would be able to function, at least for some time, by balancing those interests in a reasonable manner. But a political community has to motivate its citizens to subordinate their private interests to the public good. Both the philosopher and the Jewish scholar agree that religion is ultimately necessary to turn individuals into citizens invested in the public interest, or, as Strauss puts it at the end of his essay in a reference to Plato, “to transform natural man

into “the guardian of his city” (LRK §45, p. 140). The Natural Law as a mere framework cannot supply such a religion, as it is based only on enlightened self-interest. It cannot as such impose absolute duties. This is the fundamental reason why it is not called a complete code, as it requires guidance from outside itself to function as a foundation for political society.

The philosophic Law of Reason as a complete code could offer such guidance, insofar as it can direct political society towards a code of laws that is in accordance with the nature of man as such. But the philosophers understand human perfection as ultimately consisting in a solitary, contemplative existence that is not bound by any absolute, universal duties. All society is a means to the end of human, i.e. philosophic perfection. Society as such is, in other words, not an end in itself. Thus “the Natural Law is not obligatory and does not command, or presuppose, an inner attachment to society” (LRK §45, p. 140). The philosophers are forced to foster such an attachment by inventing political religions.

This is “the fundamental weakness of the philosophic position” in the eyes of the Jewish scholar (LRK §45, p. 140). He agrees with the philosophers regarding the necessity of a standard beyond the quasi-natural law. But he disagrees with their claim that human reason alone can supply this standard. The essentially asocial life of the philosopher cannot satisfy the desire of someone who has “a passionate interest in genuine morality,” i.e. absolute moral duties (LRK §45, p. 140). Thus, “one has not to be naturally pious (...) in order to long with all his heart for revelation” (LRK §45, p. 140). While the scholar is a believer in the revealed divine law, his ultimate objection to philosophy turns out to be essentially connected with a concern for political society and genuine morality. This is the reason why, according to Strauss, “the central part of [the scholar’s] critique of philosophy” is his critique of asceticism (LRK §29, p. 126). The philosophic life is ascetic in the sense that it is not essentially directed towards political society and moral action. The scholar is in full agreement with the king of the Khazars that not contemplation, but genuine moral action is of the highest importance to man as such.

According to the scholar, only the divinely revealed law can supply a political community with a code that is not ultimately rooted in the selfish interest of its members and that can prescribe absolute duties. The divinely revealed law is *the* alternative to the rational *nomoi* of the philosophers because it also directs political society towards an ideal that lies beyond it. However, while the necessity of a revealed law can be understood by human reason alone, a true divine law cannot be established without God’s direct intervention. Only the Jewish nation was elected by God to receive and pass on the true divine law. Hence “only the Jewish nation is eternal, all other nations are perishable; all other nations are dead, only the Jewish nation is living” (LRK §39, p. 134).

5. Halevi’s Conversion

But the position of the Jewish scholar should not be mistaken for the position of Halevi. Strauss interprets the

Kuzari as a book with both an exoteric and an esoteric teaching. As he shows throughout his essay, Halevi uses many of the rhetorical devices that philosophers like Avicenna, Aristotle, or Maimonides employed in their works (LRK §14, pp. 110-111). The Jewish scholar is merely one voice in the dialogue Halevi constructs to convey his teaching. Might then the *Kuzari* itself be an example of rational *nomoi*, a complete code that uses Jewish orthodoxy as its governmental part? Was Halevi, in other words, a philosopher?

While Strauss considers this possibility (LRK §12, pp. 106-108),¹³ he also discusses another hypothesis that is somewhat astounding. According to this second hypothesis, Halevi was deeply influenced by philosophy and at some point even “converted” to it, before he ultimately rejected it. As Strauss puts it: “[F]or some time, we prefer to think for a very short time, he was a philosopher. After that moment, a spiritual hell, he returned to the Jewish fold” (LRK §13, p. 109). While Halevi found the philosophic arguments largely convincing, he ultimately could not accept philosophy as a way of life. Strauss thus presents the unique case of what one might call a “lapsed” philosopher, a particularly curious phenomenon if we consider that Strauss had only a few pages earlier pointed out that “a genuine philosopher can never become a genuine convert to Judaism or to any other revealed religion” (LRK §11, pp. 104-105). How, then, do we have to understand Halevi’s return to “the Jewish fold”?

Laurence Lampert, in his interpretation of “The Law of Reason in the *Kuzari*,” treats Halevi’s supposed rejection of philosophy as ironic, a facetious remark by Strauss that barely hides his true conviction that Halevi was indeed a philosopher.¹⁴ Such irony is certainly not entirely foreign to Strauss’ way of writing and it is quite likely that his ultimate assessment of Halevi was different from his openly stated opinion. But it may be premature to simply dismiss Strauss statement as ironic and hence philosophically unimportant. Not only is this presentation of an author as being a strange mixture of philosophic and non-philosophic elements unique in Strauss’ oeuvre, but Strauss also points out in the essay itself that “all ambiguities occurring in good books are [due] not to chance or carelessness, but to deliberate choice, to the author’s wish to indicate a grave question” (LRK §22, p. 118). Furthermore, Strauss takes up the question of Halevi’s nature again at the end of his essay, when he speaks about Halevi’s “basic objection to philosophy” (LRK §45, p. 141). It seems necessary, then, to pose the question of why Strauss chooses to present Halevi in this ambiguous manner.

To give an answer, we have to accept Strauss’ hypothesis for the sake of the argument and consider what Halevi’s “objection to philosophy” might have been. One possibility would be that he denied philosophy on the ground of the revealed Jewish law, just like the Jewish scholar. While Strauss points out that Halevi’s “basic objection to philosophy was (...) not particularly Jewish, nor even particularly religious, but moral” (LRK §45, p. 141), these two elements would not have to be mutually exclusive. But Strauss makes clear that Halevi shared the objections of the philosophers against revealed religion (LRK §13, pp. 108-110). He even indicates what Halevi may have found particularly objectionable in the scholar’s

position: Halevi presents specifically the doctrine of the justice of God as his own and not just the scholar's teaching (LRK §6, p. 99). As mentioned before, the scholar ultimately concluded that only the true revealed law inherited by the Jewish people could supply the guidance needed by mankind. But it is hard to see, how a god can be called just, that, without any reason, gives what is needed by all human beings as such only to a particular part of mankind and denies it to everybody else. Halevi's rejection of philosophy therefore cannot be based on a particular revealed law, because the very particularity of such a law would call its genuine morality into question.

It may then be more fruitful to look towards a philosophic position that is deeply concerned with genuine morality and that can be understood as standing in opposition to what Strauss calls in his essay "the philosophic view" (LRK §38, p. 134): Kant's Practical Philosophy. Strauss' emphasis on universality as the distinctive feature of genuine morality may already remind the reader of Kant's thought. This is entirely intentional and Strauss frequently alludes to Kantian terminology in the last section of his essay, going so far as to identify genuine morality with "categorical imperatives" (LRK §45, p. 140). Even the term "Law of Reason" itself evokes Kant's *Vernunftgesetz*. One could then assume that the Halevi of Strauss' second hypothesis stands in for Kant, presenting an argument that is or at least seems to be Kantian. But it would be wrong to identify Halevi's position as simply Kantian. This becomes immediately evident when we consider that Halevi, according to Strauss, hides his true intention behind an exoteric teaching. Far from only omitting truths that may be dangerous to state openly, he presents arguments to his readers that he himself holds to be untrue. He thus shows his ultimate agreement with the position of the philosophers not only in speech, but also in deed. While the Halevi of the second hypothesis shares with Kant the concern with universal morality, he does not think such a morality possible on the basis of human reason alone. It may then be more adequate to call the position of this Halevi nihilistic in the sense that he longs for a kind of morality that he at same time holds to be impossible. The philosophers teach truths that prove deadly, "a spiritual hell" (LRK §13, p. 109). By writing in an exoteric manner, Halevi protects the majority of his readers when he argues for religion and soothes the doubts they may harbor, while showing the true bleakness of the human condition only to those readers that are capable of becoming aware of the problem on their own.

Strauss' presentation of Halevi thus seems to be intended to evoke concepts strongly connected with modern, especially Kantian and post-Kantian philosophy. This puts the argument of his essay in a wider context than the original opposition of a "philosophic" and a "theological" view. "Philosophy" makes its first appearance in the text as part of an open question and Strauss' allusion to Kant invites the reader to consider the difference between ancient and modern philosophy in regard to morality and the question of "what a philosopher is" (LRK §1, p. 95). But the ambiguity of Halevi's position also leads the reader to reconsider the unity of the classical philosophic tradition itself. As already mentioned, Strauss starts his essay by calling out a philosophic and a theological position concerning the Natural Law and connects them to two me-

dieval thinkers, Marsilius of Padua and Thomas Aquinas.¹⁵ But in the same place he also identifies both thinkers as "Christian Aristotelians" (LRK §2, p. 96). Later on, he points out that "philosophy is not identical with Aristotelianism" (LRK §16, p. 112). Thus, what may at first glance appear to be a simple opposition of philosophers and believers turns out to be a more complex situation. The believers, on the one hand, draw on the philosophic tradition of, e.g., Aristotelianism, while the philosophers, on the other hand, may not be as unconcerned with the moral law as one might think. Halevi's ambiguity towards philosophy for moral reasons serves as a demonstration of the ambiguities present in the philosophic tradition as a whole.

6. Strauss' Intention

We may then say that Strauss' intention in writing "The Law of Reason in the *Kuzari*" goes beyond the desire for a clearer presentation of a certain understanding of philosophy and the philosopher. It also goes beyond emphasizing the fundamental opposition between the philosophic life and the demands of revealed religion. While Strauss stresses the necessity of a refutation of the "very possibility of Divine revelation in the precise sense of the term" (LRK §12, p. 107) for the philosopher, he also shows a more general aspect of this question by drawing the connection between the concern with morality and the belief in a revealed law. "Moral man as such is the potential believer" (LRK §45, p. 140) and insofar as the potential philosopher is also a moral man, i.e. someone concerned with politics and the fate of his fellow citizens, he will have to consider both morality and religious belief in their interconnectedness to understand his own position.

This is also true for Leo Strauss himself. The historical Halevi was an early proponent of a return of the Jewish people to the Holy Land and died on a pilgrimage to Jerusalem. Therefore he was later sometimes hailed as a medieval precursor of Zionism. If we consider the importance of Zionism for the young Leo Strauss, it may not seem entirely accidental that he chose Halevi in particular as an example of a philosophic thinker concerned with morality and the defense of Judaism.¹⁶

"The Law of Reason in the *Kuzari*" can thus ultimately be understood as being in service to what is most important to every philosopher: self-understanding.

Notes

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¹ L. STRAUSS, *The Law of Reason in the Kuzari*, in: Leo Strauss, *Persecution and the Art of Writing*, Free Press, Glencoe, Ill. 1952, pp. 95-141. Citations from the essay will be indicated as LRK with paragraph and page throughout this paper.

² For Halevi's biography see: J. YAHALOM, *Yehuda Halevi: Poetry and Pilgrimage*, Hebrew University Magnes Press, Jerusalem 2009.

³ Cf. A. SHEAR, *The Kuzari and the Shaping of Jewish Identity, 1167-1900*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge 2008.

⁴ Cf. K. BROOK, *The Jews of Khazaria*, Rowman and Littlefield Publishers, Lanham 2006 (2nd Edition); P. GOLDEN, *The Conversion of the Khazars to Judaism*, in P. Golden / H. Ben-Schammai / A. Róna-Tas

(ed. by), *The World of the Khazars: New Perspectives. Selected Papers from the Jerusalem 1999 International Khazar Colloquium*. Handbook of Oriental Studies Sect. 8 Vol. 17, Brill, Leiden 2007, pp. 123-162.

⁵ Cf. LRK §7-10, pp. 100-104.

⁶ First publication in: "Proceedings of the American Academy for Jewish Research", 13, 1943, pp. 47-96.

⁷ Cf. K. H. GREEN, *Religion, Philosophy and Morality. How Leo Strauss Read Judah Halevi's Kuzari*, in "Journal of the American Academy of Religion", 61, 1993, pp. 225-273; L. LAMPERT, *The Enduring Importance of Leo Strauss*, University of Chicago Press, Chicago 2013, pp. 32-71.

⁸ LAMPERT, *Importance*, p. 32.

⁹ MARSILIUS OF PADUA, *Defensor pacis*, I. c. 19, sect. 13; MARSILIUS OF PADUA, *The Defender of the Peace*, translated by Annabel Brett, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge 2005, p. 136. Cf. LRK §2, p. 96 n. 2.

¹⁰ Strauss consistently shifts from "Law of Reason" to "rational *nomoi*" and "rational laws" when speaking more specifically about the text of the *Kuzari*. Cf. LRK §4, p. 98; LRK §16, p. 112 with LRK §19, pp. 114-115; LRK §22, p. 118; LRK §26, p. 122; LRK §29-30, pp. 126-127; LRK §31, p. 128; LRK §42-45, pp. 136-140.

¹¹ Strauss uses this term here in the traditional sense of a *theologia civilis*, signifying the employment of religious teachings as a means to purely political ends. Cf. AUGUSTINUS, *De Civitate Dei*, VI. c. 5-12. It should not be confused with the meaning that "political theology" has attained more recently. Cf. H. MEIER, *Die Lehre Carl Schmitts. Vier Kapitel zur Unterscheidung Politischer Theologie und Politischer Philosophie*, J.B. Metzler, Stuttgart 2012 (4th Edition), pp. 291-293.

¹² This is the context in which Aristotle introduces the term: ARISTOTLE, *Politics*, VII 1324a 25-33. Cf. for the concept of the "philosophic life" in Strauss' thinking: H. MEIER, *Politische Philosophie und die Herausforderung des Offenbarungsglaubens*, C.H. Beck, München 2013, pp. 43-46 with n. 6.

¹³ Cf. LAMPERT, *Importance*, pp. 39-45.

¹⁴ LAMPERT, *Importance*, pp. 45-47.

¹⁵ Marsilius of Padua and Thomas Aquinas also appear together in *Natural Right and History*, representing the two alternative interpretations of Aristotle's natural right teaching. Strauss in a footnote even refers the reader to *The Law of Reason in the Kuzari*. It is almost the only footnote in the entire book that points towards one of Strauss' own works. Cf. L. STRAUSS, *Natural Right and History*, University of Chicago Press, Chicago 1953, pp. 157-164 with n. 32.

¹⁶ The only biographical article Strauss cites in his essay emphasizes the political aspect of Halevi's life and writing: S. BARON, *Yehudah Halevi: An Answer to an Historic Challenge*, in: "Jewish Social Studies", 3, 1941, pp. 243-272. See especially LRK §13, p. 109 n. 38, which points to a passage in Baron's article opposing the "hard and fast realities of [Halevi's] age" to the futility of studying the "wisdom of the Greeks" (BARON, *Yehuda Halevi*, p. 259). Cf. LAMPERT, *Importance*, p. 37 n. 8.